
**Late Maastrichtian *Anomoeodus cf. subclavatus* (Agassiz, 1833) from the
Jauche Member in Orp-Jauche (Belgium)**

Nick VAN LIEFFERINGE

TAXONOMY

Kingdom: Animalia
Phylum: Chordata
Class: Actinopterygii
Order: Pycnodontiformes
Family: Pycnodontidae
Genus: *Anomoeodus*
Species: *Anomoeodus cf. subclavatus*
Author Citation: Agassiz, 1833

Anomoeodus cf. subclavatus
reniform crushing tooth

1 cm

GEOLOGICAL TIME SCALE

Eon: Phanerozoic
Era: Mesozoic
Period: Cretaceous
Sub Period: None
Epoch: Late
International Age: Maastrichtian

STRATIGRAPHY

Chalk Group

Jauche Member (part of the Late Cretaceous strata at Orp-Jauche, Belgium)

PROVENANCE

Collector: Nick Van Liefferinge (NVL)

Date Collected: 21/02/2026

Acquired by: Field collection

LOCATION

Jauche-la-Marne

Orp-Jauche

Walloon Brabant

Belgium

REFERENCES

Friedman M. 2012: Ray-finned fishes (Osteichthyes, Actinopterygii) from the type Maastrichtian, The Netherlands and Belgium, in: Jagt J.W.M., Donovan S.K. & Jagt-Yazykova (ed.), *Fossils of the type Maastrichtian, Part 1, Scripta Geologica, Special Issue 8*, pp. 113-142.

Robaszynski F., Dhondt A.V. & Jagt J.W.M. 2001: The Jauche Member, 01/01/2001. National Commission for Stratigraphy Belgium.
(<https://ncs.naturalsciences.be/lithostratigraphy/Jauche-Member>)